

Substituted-1,8-naphthyridines. Part-IV. Synthesis of 2-Methyl-N-aryl-1,8-naphthyridine-3-carboxamides

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1,8-Naphthyridine derivatives exhibit a wide spectrum of biological activities such as antibacterial^{1,2}, antimalarial³, anticancer⁴ and diuretic⁵. Encouraged by the reports and in continuation of our work in this field⁶⁻⁹, we report here the synthesis and antibacterial activity of a series of substituted 1,8-naphthyridines (3).

The present work deals with a facile one-step synthesis of 2-methyl-N-aryl-1,8-naphthyridine-3-carboxamides (3), involving the condensation of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde (1) with acetoacetanilides (2) in methanol with a trace of piperidine. The formation of 3 was confirmed by the unambiguous synthesis of 3 (R=C₆H₅) involving the reaction of ethyl-2-methyl-1,8-naphthyridine-3-carboxylate (4) with aniline in the presence of xylene and pyridine. The compounds (3; R=C₆H₅) obtained by the two methods were identical in all respects (m.p., m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir).

The structures of these compounds were in conformity with their elemental analyses and spectral data. The ir spectra of 3 exhibited two bands at 1 670 and 3 220 cm⁻¹ for amide carbonyl and amide-NH, respectively, and an intense band at 1 600 cm⁻¹ attributable to C=N. The spectra also exhibited bands at 1 540, 1 440, 1 320, 1 260, 1 180, 910 and 840 cm⁻¹. The pmr spectrum of 3a (R=C₆H₅) in TFA (chemical shift in δ ppm downfield from TMS internal reference) showed a three-proton singlet at δ 3.4 due to methyl group. The protons at C-4, C-5 and C-7 resonated as multiplets centred at δ 8.9, 9.0 and 9.2, respectively. The C-6 proton and amide NH proton appeared alongwith five aromatic protons as a complex multiplet at δ 7.3-8.4. The mass spectra of 3 exhibited strong molecular ion peaks consistent with their elemental analyses. The mass spectra of 3 (R=C₆H₅) and 3 (R=*o*-Cl-C₆H₄) showed strong M⁺ peaks at *m/z* 263 and 297, respectively.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF 2-METHYL-N-ARYL-1,8-NAPHTHYRIDINE-3-CARBOXAMIDES (3)*

Compd. no.	R	M.p. °C	Molecular formula	Analyses % : Found/(Calcd.)		
				C	H	N
3a	C ₆ H ₅	215	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ O	73.06 (73.00)	4.90 (4.94)	15.85 (15.96)
3b	2-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	185	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O	73.51 (73.64)	5.38 (5.42)	5.11 (5.16)
3c	3-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	160	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O	73.54 (73.64)	5.30 (5.42)	5.12 (5.16)
3d	4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	170	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O	73.60 (73.64)	5.40 (5.42)	5.10 (5.16)
3e	2-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	300	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂	69.51 (69.62)	5.05 (5.12)	14.20 (14.33)
3f	3-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	210	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂	69.57 (69.62)	5.06 (5.12)	14.26 (14.33)
3g	4-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	150	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂	69.50 (69.62)	5.05 (5.12)	14.23 (14.33)
3h	2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	190	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂	68.71 (68.82)	4.60 (4.66)	15.05 (15.05)
3i	3-OH.C ₆ H ₄	250	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂	68.70 (68.82)	4.58 (4.66)	15.01 (15.05)
3j	2-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	150	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₂ OCl	64.54 (64.64)	4.00 (4.04)	14.06 (14.14)
3k	3-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	240	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₂ OCl	64.50 (64.64)	4.01 (4.04)	14.08 (14.14)
3l	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	205	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₂ OCl	64.52 (64.64)	4.00 (4.04)	14.08 (14.14)
3m	3-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	170	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂	62.55 (62.34)	3.96 (3.90)	18.10 (18.18)
3n	3-COOH.C ₆ H ₄	305	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₃	66.25 (66.45)	4.16 (4.23)	13.52 (13.68)
3o	3-COOH.C ₆ H ₄	130	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₃	66.27 (66.45)	4.19 (4.23)	13.55 (13.68)

* Obtained in 65-85% yield.

Antibacterial activity: All the compounds were screened for antibacterial activity by filter paper disc technique¹⁰ using a species of gram-positive bacteria, *i.e.* *S. albus* and *B. subtilis* and a species of gram-negative bacteria, *i.e.* *E. coli* and *P. vulgaris*. None of the compounds was found to possess any significant activity.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in capillary tubes using a sulphuric-acid-bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 283 spectrophotometer, 60 MHz pmr spectra in TFA on a Varian spectrometer using TMS as internal standard, and mass spectra on a Varian MAT CH-7 instrument at 70 eV. The homogeneity and purity of the compounds were tested through tlc.

The substituted-acetoacetanilides^{11,12} and ethyl-2-methyl-1,8-naphthyridine-3-carboxylate¹³ were prepared according to the procedures reported in the literature.

2-Methyl-N-aryl-1,8-naphthyridine-3-carboxamides (3): (a) A mixture of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde (1; 0.1 mol) and appropriate acetoacetanilide (2; 0.1 mol) was refluxed in methanol (25 ml) in the presence of a catalytic amount of piperidine for 4 h. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool and poured into crushed ice. The separated solid was filtered and recrystallised from methanol (Table 1). (b) A mixture of ethyl-2-methyl-1,8-naphthyridine-3-carboxylate (4; 0.1 mol), aniline (0.01 mol) and pyridine (5 drops) in xylene (20 ml) was refluxed for 5 h. After the reaction, xylene was removed and the residual mass cooled. The separated solid was filtered, dried and recrystallised from methanol.

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Synthesis of the Anhydrosulphide of Alkylxanthic Acid

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FORMATION of anhydrosulphide of ethyl xanthic acid were reported¹⁻³ through the reaction of potassium ethyl xanthate and ethyl chloroformate. Xanthic acid disulphides on treatment with KCN were reported⁴ to give anhydrosulphides. Simmons *et al.*⁵ have also reported the preparation of anhydrosulphide of ethylxanthic acid by the reaction of tetracyanodithiin with potassium-ethyl-xanthate. The direct formation of anhydrosulphides from the xanthate reaction was observed by Willcox⁶, during the reaction of potassium ethyl xanthate and ether solution of acetyl chloride at room temperature. We now report the formation of anhydrosulphide of alkylxanthic acids (5) from the reaction of sym. phthaloyl dichloride (1) and excess of potassium-O-alkyl-xanthates at room temperature.

The probable mechanism for the formation of anhydrosulphide (5) involves the intervention of unsymmetrical phthaloyl dixanthates (2)⁷, which is supported by reactions of the latter with potassium-O-alkyl-xanthates (Scheme 1) to obtain the corresponding anhydrosulphides (5a-c). We have also isolated thiophthalic anhydride (4) from the above reaction mixture. However our attempt to isolate thiophthalic anhydride (3) from the reaction mixture was not successful which showed that thiophthalic anhydride (3) rapidly changes to thiophthalic anhydride⁸ (4).

Experimental

Reaction of sym. phthaloyl dichloride (1) with excess of potassium-O-isopropyl-xanthate: Compound 5a: Phthaloyl dichloride (2.03 g, 0.01 mol) was taken in acetone (50 ml). To this, potassium-O-isopropyl-xanthate (6.96 g, 0.04 mol) was added below 0° and stirring was continued for 30 min at 0° and further 30 min at room temperature. Evaporation of solvent after removal of unreacted potassium-O-isopropyl-xanthate yielded thiophthalic anhydride⁸ (1 g, 61%), m.p. 110° (m.m.p.) and anhydrosulphide of isopropyl xanthic acid (5a; 1.4 g, 59%), m.p. 52-4° (lit. 54°)⁴, (Found: C, 39.44; H, 5.50. C₈H₁₄O₂S₂, calcd. for: C, 40.33;